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Research Article

**DESIGN CHARACTERIZATION & EVALUATION OF
ACRIVASTINE BUCCAL PATCHES****Guguloth Kavya¹, Dr.G.S. Valluri², Dr.Gampa Vijay Kumar³**¹KGR Institute Of Technology And Management, Rampally, Kesara, Rangareddy, Telangana, India.²Assistant Professor, KGR Institute of Technology and Management, Rampally, Kesara, Rangareddy, Telangana, India.³Professor And Head Department of Pharmacy, KGR Institute Of Technology And Management, Rampally, Kesara, Rangareddy, Telangana, India.**Abstract**

Acrivastine is a medication used for the treatment of allergies and hay fever. It is a second-generation H1-receptor antagonist antihistamine (like its base molecule triprolidine) and works by blocking histamine H1 receptors. In the present study buccal drug delivery of Acrivastine was developed Matrix type of buccal patches was developed by using polymers Carbopol 940, chitosan and Eudragit S 100. Buccal patches were prepared by employing solvent casting method. Propylene glycol and Tween80 were selected as permeation enhancer and plasticizer. Drug excipient compatibility studies were carried out by using FTIR, and it was observed that there were no interactions. Formulations were prepared by taking Carbopol 940, chitosan and Eudragit S 100 as polymers in the concentrations of 100 mg, 200 mg and 300 mg from F1-F9 formulations, and all the formulations were evaluated for various physical parameters Physical appearance, Flatness, Weight variation, Thickness, Folding endurance, Drug content, Moisture uptake, Moisture content and Swelling study and all the results were found to be within the pharmacopeial limits, invitro drug release studies by using dialysis membrane. Among all the 9 formulations F7 formulation which contain Eudragit S 100 100mg had shown 95.76% cumulative drug release with in 12 hours. For F7 formulation release kinetics were plotted and the Regression coefficient value was found to be high for Higuchi release model i.e., 0.993.

Key words: *Acrivastine, Buccal Patches and Buccal Drug Delivery, Carbopol 940, chitosan and Eudragit S 100***Corresponding author:****Dr. Gampa Vijay Kumar,**

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INTRODUCTION:

Buccal route of drug delivery provides the direct access to the systemic circulation through the jugular vein bypassing the first pass hepatic metabolism leading to high bioavailability. Other advantages such as excellent accessibility, low enzymatic activity, suitability for drugs or excipients that mildly and reversibly damage or irritate the mucosa, painless administration, easy withdrawal, facility to include permeation enhancer/ enzyme inhibitor or pH modifier in the formulation, versatility in designing as multidirectional or unidirectional release system for local or systemic action.

MATERIALS:

Acrivastine, Carbopol 940, Chitosan, Eudragit S 100, Dichloromethane, Methanol, Peg 400,

TWEEN 80 all the chemicals used were laboratory grade.

METHODOLOGY:**Formulation:**

Development of Buccal patches : Buccal drug delivery patches were prepared by solvent casting method.

HPMCK4M and HPMCK100M were weighed in requisite

ratios and they were then dissolved in dichloromethane and ethanol as solvent using magnetic stirrer. Acrivastine (100mg), Propylene glycol and Tween 80

was added to the above dispersion under continuous stirring. The uniform dispersion was poured in the petri plate. The rate of evaporation of solvent was controlled by inverting cut funnel over the patches..

Table 1 : Formulations of Acrivastine Buccal Patch

INGREDIENTS	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9
DRUG(mg)	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
Carbopol 940(mg)	100	200	300	-	-	-	-	-	-
Chitosan(mg)	-	-	-	100	200	300	-	-	-
Eudragit S 100(mg)	-	-	-	-	-	-	100	200	300
DICHLOROMETHANE(ml)	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10
METHANOL(ml)	13.2	13.2	13.2	13.2	13.2	13.2	13.2	13.2	13.2
PEG 400(ml)	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
TWEEN 80(ml)	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1

Evaluation Of Prepared patches

The designed patches were evaluated for physical appearance, thickness, weight variation, flatness, folding endurance, moisture uptake, moisture content, drug content determination, surface pH, In vitro permeation studies using dialysis membrane.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION:**Standard Calibration curve of Acrivastine:**

Table 2: Concentration and absorbance obtained for calibration curve of Acrivastine in pH 6.8

S. No.	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Absorbance* (at 274 nm)
1	0.5	0.126
2	1	0.248
3	1.5	0.362
4	2	0.487
5	2.5	0.599
6	3	0.723

It was found that the estimation of Acrivastine by UV spectrophotometric method at λ_{max} 274 nm in 6.8 pH phosphate buffer had good reproducibility and this method was used in the study. The correlation coefficient for the standard curve was found to be closer to 1, at the concentration range, 2-10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$.

Figure 1: Standard graph of Acrivastine in pH 6.8 Phosphate buffer

EVALUATION OF ACRIVASTINE BUCCAL PATCHES :

Physical appearance : All the Buccal patches were visually inspected for colour, clarity, flexibility.

Flatness : All the Buccal patches was found to be flat with out any foams.

Table 3 : Evaluation of Buccal patch by physical methods

Formulation	Thickness (mm)	Folding endurance	Drug content (%)	Moisture uptake (%)	Moisture content (%)	Surface pH
F1	0.3658	21	67	7.65	3.67	6.28
F2	0.3476	24	69	25.87	8.3	6.32
F3	0.3432	25	58.6	12.62	5.56	5.47
F4	0.3432	22	69	14.76	6.02	6.23
F5	0.3287	28	65.8	12.63	5.67	6.17
F6	0.3897	31	79.82	16.68	11.69	5.82
F7	0.3458	29	59.87	18.98	9.76	6.23
F8	0.3218	27	63.42	17.26	6.98	6.73
F9	0.3276	23	57.16	16.25	7.69	6.82

The prepared Acrivastine Buccal patches were evaluated by physical methods such as Physical appearance, Flatness, Weight variation, Thickness, Folding endurance, Drug content, Moisture uptake and Moisture content and all the results were found to be with in the pharmacopeial limits.

In Vitro Permeation Study

Table 4 : Evaluation of Buccal patch by In-vitro permeation studies using dialysis membrane

Time(hrs)	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9
1	16.45	21.34	29.19	15.66	18.54	28.35	27.89	36.43	16.45
2	24.64	38.79	45.32	34.16	29.73	47.8	36.38	48.18	24.64
4	37.11	52.99	59.13	55.78	35.04	60.24	51.06	59.89	37.11
6	47.87	64.88	63.63	63.01	45.56	68.73	62.52	65.53	47.87
8	56.59	71.46	69.71	72.88	59.25	71.34	78.88	69.43	56.59
10	68.34	78.23	79.27	83.26	69.41	82.17	89.56	79.98	68.34
12	71.22	82.98	89.86	85.35	79.85	89.75	95.76	88.52	71.22

Figure 2 : Dissolution profile of F1to F9 formulations

Discussion: Among all the 9 formulations F7 formulation which contain Eudragit S 100 100mg had shown 95.76% cumulative drug release with in 12 hours.

Drug Release Kinetics

Table 5 :Release kinetics of In-vitro permeation studies using dialysis membrane

CUMULATIVE (%) RELEASE Q	TIME (T)	ROOT (T)	LOG(%) RELEASE	LOG (T)	LOG (%) REMAIN
0	0	0			2.000
27.89	1	1.000	1.445	0.000	1.858
36.38	2	1.414	1.561	0.301	1.804
51.06	4	2.000	1.708	0.602	1.690
62.52	6	2.449	1.796	0.778	1.574
78.88	8	2.828	1.897	0.903	1.325
89.56	10	3.162	1.952	1.000	1.019

95.76	12	3.464	1.981	1.079	0.627
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Figure 3 : Zero order kinetics

Figure 4 : Higuchi plot

Figure 5 : Peppas plot

Figure 6: First order kinetics

DISCUSSION:

For F7 formulation release kinetics were plotted and the Regression coefficient value was found to be high for Higuchi release model i.e., 0.993.

SUMMARY & CONCLUSION:

In present study buccal drug delivery of Acrivastine was developed. Matrix type of buccal patches was developed by using polymers Carbopol 940, chitosan and Eudragit S 100. Buccal patches were prepared by employing solvent casting method. Propylene glycol and Tween80 were selected as permeation enhancer and plasticizer. Drug excipient compatibility studies were carried out by using FTIR, and it was observed that there were no interactions. Formulations were prepared with the varying concentrations polymers ranging from F1-F9, and all the formulations were evaluated for various physical parameters Physical

appearance, Flatness, Weight variation, Thickness, Folding endurance, Drug content, Moisture uptake, Moisture content and Swelling study and all the results were found to be within the pharmacopeial limits, invitro drug release studies by using dialysis membrane. Among all the 9 formulations F7 formulation which contain Eudragit S 100 100mg had shown 95.76% cumulative drug release with in 12 hours. For F7 formulation release kinetics were plotted and the Regression coefficient value was found to be high for Higuchi release model i.e., 0.993.

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